

Photochemical Reaction between Cinnamic Acid and Chlorine in Carbon Tetrachloride Solution.

By KALI PADA BASU.

There is a great deal of controversy at present regarding the primary action of light on chlorine. One school (Chapman, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1925, **21**, 547) holds that activated chlorine molecules are primarily formed. Franck (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1925, **21**, 536), suggests that absorption of light of shorter wavelength than 4785\AA , the long wavelength limit of the continuous absorption region, leads to the dissociation of a chlorine molecule into an excited and a normal atom. Weigert (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, **106**, 407), on the other hand, postulates that the presence of moisture in chlorine is essential for the primary photochemical process and that in its absence the light absorbed by chlorine molecules is given out as isochromatic fluorescence.

The present investigation was taken up with a view to throw some light, if possible, on the action of light on chlorine, and forms the first communication on a series of photochemical reactions involving chlorine undertaken by the present author.

Nasareff (*Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1919, **18**, 231), determined the temperature coefficient of the action of chlorine on cinnamic acid in white light and found it to be 1.4. The bromination has been done in this laboratory by Ghosh and Purakayastha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 409).

Chlorine, in these experiments, was prepared by the action of pure hydrochloric acid on potassium permanganate, washed successively through water, sulphuric acid, anhydrous carbon tetrachloride in an all-glass apparatus and then dissolved in pure dry carbon tetrachloride. The carbon tetrachloride was guaranteed to be free from sulphur and was freed from traces of moisture by shaking with and keeping over anhydrous calcium chloride and redistillation. This is a very important step as will appear presently.

Before chlorination experiments can be profitably followed in carbon tetrachloride solutions, one must be sure that there is no reaction between chlorine and carbon tetrachloride as is claimed

by Plotnikow (*Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1919, 19, 22). It was found that solutions of chlorine in ordinary carbon tetrachloride showed a slow reaction whereas perfectly dry carbon tetrachloride was not affected by chlorine either in darkness or in light. This is in agreement with the observations of Benrath and Hertel (*Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1924, 23, 30). Presence of traces of moisture in Nasareff's carbon tetrachloride probably accounts for the slow reaction between cinnamic acid and chlorine in the dark.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Merck's "extra pure" cinnamic acid was further purified by crystallising twice. The reaction vessel employed was a cell (4 cm. in length and breadth and 1 cm. depth) made of optically pure glass. It had a very narrow opening at the top provided with a closely fitting stopper. The velocity of the reaction was determined by pipetting out 2 c.c. from time to time and followed iodometrically with N/500 sodium thiosulphate which was freshly prepared and standardised before each experiment. Preliminary experiments at 22.6° with M/60 chlorine solutions in the reaction cell indicated that loss due to evaporation as 2 c.c. were successively withdrawn by a pipette was negligible.

The Dark Reaction.

At 22.6°, the temperature at which most of the experiments in light were carried out, the dark reaction, as Table I will indicate, was negligible.

TABLE I.

The Dark Reaction.

Cinnamic acid = M/30;		Chlorine = M/80;		Temp. = 22.6°.	
Time in mins.	...	0	115	330	1260
N/500 Thiosulphate in c.c.	...	25.0	24.9	24.4	22.4
Unimol. const. log $a/(a-x)$00004	.00004

The photochemical investigations were carried out with a quartz mercury lamp as the source of light. The chlorination was very slow with a 1000 c. p. Point-o-lite lamp as the source. The kinetics of the reaction was studied in white light with a 4 cm.

water filter, the reaction cell being at a distance of 12 cm. from the mercury lamp which was run from a storage battery with a constant current of 3 amp. The reaction cell was maintained at a constant temperature by placing it inside a double-jacketted copper box through which water at a constant temperature from a thermostat was circulated by means of a pump. As the following tables will show the light reaction is perfectly unimolecular with respect to chlorine, and the value of the constant is independent of the concentration of chlorine. A large number of experiments were carried out, only a few typical results are appended. The unimolecular constants are all on the basis of logarithms to the base 10 and the time is reckoned in minutes.

TABLE II.

Cinnamic acid = $M/30$; Chlorine = $M/60$; Temp. = 22.6° .

Time in mins.	...	0	15	35	55	80	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	34.1	29.8	24.8	20.6	17.0		
Unimol. const.0039	.0040	.0040	.0038	Mean .0039

TABLE III.

Cinnamic acid = $M/30$; Chlorine = $M/100$; Temp. = 22.6° .

Time in mins.	...	0	15	35	60	85	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	21.2	18.35	15.5	12.55	10.0		
Unimol. const.0042	.0039	.0038	.0038	Mean .0039

TABLE IV.

Cinnamic acid = $M/30$; Chlorine = $M/175$; Temp. = 22.6° .

Time in mins.	...	0	10	25	45	75	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	11.4	10.45	9.2	7.95	5.95		
Unimol. const.0038	.0037	.0035	.0038	Mean .0037

Experiments showed that the reaction was zero-molecular with respect to cinnamic acid. The value of the unimolecular constant

was unaffected when the concentration of cinnamic acid was the same as or even lower than the concentration of chlorine. Tables V, VI and VII will make it clear.

TABLE V.

Cinnamic acid = $M/60$;		Chlorine = $M/60$;			Temp. = 22.6° .	
Time in mins. ...	0	15	35	60	85	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	34.2	30.0	24.9	19.25	15.4	
Unimol. const.0038	.0039	.0041	.0040	Mean .0035

TABLE VI.

Cinnamic acid = $M/100$;		Chlorine = $M/110$;			Temp. = 22.6° .	
Time in mins. ...	0	15	35	62	85	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	18.75	16.45	13.9	11.2	9.5	
Unimol. const.0038	.0037	.0036	.0035	Mean .0036

TABLE VII.

Cinnamic acid = $M/100$;		Chlorine = $M/60$;		Temp. = 22.6° .	
Time in mins.	$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	Unimol. constant.			
0	34.35	
10	31.3	.0034		...	
25	27.85	.0036		.0038	
45	23.30	.0037		.0039	
65	19.30	.0038		.0039	
	Mean	.0036		.0039	

If, however, the concentration of cinnamic acid employed was very low ($M/150$), the value of the unimolecular constant diminished. Table VIII will make it clear.

TABLE VIII.

Cinnamic acid = $M/150$;		Chlorine = $M/100$;			Temp. = 22.6° .	
Time in mins. ...	0	15	35	55	79	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	19.9	18.1	16.1	14.45	12.2	
Unimol. const.0027	.0026	.0025	.0027	Mean .0026

Experiments were then performed in monochromatic light to determine the temperature coefficient and the quantum efficiency of the reaction and to see how these varied with the wavelength of incident light. The following filters, recommended by Weigert ("Optische Methoden der Chemie," 1928, p. 62) were employed.

For 436 $\mu\mu$.—(1) Rhodamin B (0.0075 gm.) and 2 gm. quinine sulphate and 6 c. c. $N\cdot H_2SO_4$ in 100 c.c.—2 cm. layer.

(2) Water filter—2 cm.

For 404 $\mu\mu$.—(1) Diamant fuchsine (big crystals. 0.03 gm.) and 4 gm. quinine hydrochloride in 100 c.c. of 96 % alcohol,—2 cm. layer.

(2) Copper sulphate (30 gm. in 100 c.c.)—2 cm. layer.

For 366.5 $\mu\mu$.—By giving a preliminary exposure to a photographic plate in a quartz spectrograph it was found that the glass cells employed transmitted the lines 366.5 $\mu\mu$ almost undiminished. Transmission began to diminish after 350 $\mu\mu$ and ceased altogether at 324 $\mu\mu$. The following filters were employed.

(1) Nitrosodimethylaniline (0.0007 %) and methyl violet R—2 cm.

(2) Copper sulphate (50 gm. in 100 c. c.)—2 cm.

The light transmitted at 404 $\mu\mu$ and at 366.5 $\mu\mu$ was very feeble. The intensity measurements were carried out with a Moll-thermopile and a Moll-galvanometer calibrated with a Hefner lamp at a distance of 100 cm. Although several experiments were carried out only one experiment at each wavelength is appended since the velocity constant is independent of the concentration of the acid and chlorine.

TABLE IX.

Experiment at 436 $\mu\mu$.

Intensity of the incident light—2.3 Hefners at 100 cm.

Cinnamic acid = $M/60$; Chlorine = $M/83$; Temp. = 22.6°.

Time in mins. ...	0	53	145	267	363
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	24.6	23.4	21.7	19.5	18.0
Unimol. const.00041	.00038	.00038	.00037	Mean .00038

Since the dark reaction had a constant (*vide* Table I) equal to 0.00004, the pure light reaction constant equals 0.00034.

TABLE X.

Experiment at 404 $\mu\mu$.

Intensity of the incident light—0.25 Hefners at 100 cm.

Cinnamic acid = $M/60$; Chlorine = $M/87$; Temp. = 22.6°.

Time in mins. ...	0	60	210	347	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	22.9	22.2	20.8	19.5	
Unimol. const.00022	.00020	.00020	Mean .00021

The pure light reaction constant is, therefore, 0.00017.

TABLE XI.

Experiment at 366.5 $\mu\mu$.

Intensity of the incident light—0.2 Hefners at 100 cm.

Cinnamic acid = $M/60$; Chlorine = $M/83$; Temp. = 22.6°.

Time in mins. ...	0	60	150	270	380	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	24.05	23.2	22.05	20.8	19.5	
Unimol. const.00026	.00025	.00024	.00024	Mean .00025

The light reaction constant, therefore, amounts to 0.00021.

Quantum efficiency at different wave-length.—Light absorbed by chlorine was found out by taking a galvanometer reading with the reaction cell filled with carbon tetrachloride and the latter filled with the chlorine solutions of the requisite strength. The difference gave the light absorbed. The Hefner lamp at 100 cm. corresponding to an energy of 900 ergs. per sq. cm. per sec. (Gerlach's value) gave a galvanometer deflection of 100 mm. A deflection of 1 mm. therefore, corresponded to 9 ergs. per sq. cm. per sec.

Wave-length 436 $\mu\mu$.—The light absorbed corresponded to 24 mm. of galvanometer deflection. No. of quanta absorbed per sq. cm. per sec. therefore,

$$= 24 \times 9 \times \frac{436 \times 10^{-7}}{3 \times 10^{10}} \times \frac{1}{6.5 \times 10^{-27}} = 4.8 \times 10^{13}$$

The change in chlorine concentration (Table IX) equals 1.2 c.c. N/500 in 2 c.c. in 53 mins. Of this 34/38 represents the light reaction. No. of mols. changed per sq. cm. per second

$$= \frac{1.2}{2} \times \frac{34}{38} \times \frac{1}{53 \times 60} \times \frac{1}{1000 \times 1000} \times 6.1 \times 10^{23}$$

$$= 1.01 \times 10^{14}.$$

The quantum efficiency is, therefore, equal to 2 mols. per quantum.

Wave-length 404 $\mu\mu$.—The light absorbed corresponded to 6 mm. No. of quanta absorbed per sq. cm. per second

$$= 6 \times 9 \times \frac{404 \times 10^{-7}}{3 \times 10^{10}} \times \frac{1}{6.5 \times 10^{-27}} = 1.1 \times 10^{13}.$$

The change in chlorine concentration (Table X) equals 0.7 c.c. N/500 in 2 c.c. in 60 mins. Of this 17/21 represents light reaction. Number of molecules transformed per sq. cm. per second, therefore, amounts to 4.7×10^{13} . The quantum efficiency is, therefore, 4 molecules per quantum.

Wave-length 366.5 $\mu\mu$.—The light absorbed amounted to 5 mm. No. of quanta absorbed per sq. cm. per second, therefore, equals 8.4×10^{12} . The number of molecules transformed per sq. cm. per sec. (Table XI) amounts to 6.0×10^{13} . The quantum efficiency is thus 7 mols. per quantum.

The quantum efficiency is thus very near to unity at $436\mu\mu$., and gradually increases with the increase in frequency.

Temperature coefficient at different wave-lengths.

Before we can be certain about the light reaction at 32.6° we must determine the dark reaction and the loss of chlorine by evaporation at that temperature. Table XII indicates the dark reaction at 32.6° .

TABLE XII.

Dark Reaction.

Cinnamic acid = M/60;		Chlorine = M/83;		Temp. = 32.6° .	
Time in mins. ...	0	30	114	205	372
N/500 Thiosulphate in c.c.	23.9	23.8	23.6	23.1	22.7
Unimol. const.00006	.00005	.00007	.00006 Mean .00006

Experiments were then carried out in monochromatic lights of the same intensity as before. Only one result at each wave-length is given.

TABLE XIII.

Experiment at 436 $\mu\mu$.

Cinnamic acid = $M/60$;	Chlorine = $M/83$;	Temp. = 32.6°.
Time in mins. ...	0 55 145 250 330	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	23.85 22.3 19.9 17.7 15.8	
Unimol. const.00053 .00054 .00052 .00054	Mean .00053

The light reaction constant is, therefore, 0.00047.

TABLE XIV.

Experiment at 404 $\mu\mu$.

Cinnamic acid = $M/60$;	Chlorine = $M/83$;	Temp. = 32.6°.
Time in mins. ...	0 60 135 240 345	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	23.6 22.7 21.65 20.05 19.0	
Unimol. const.00028 .00028 .00030 .00027	Mean .00028

The light reaction constant is thus 0.00022.

TABLE XV.

Experiment at 366.5 $\mu\mu$.

Cinnamic acid = $M/60$;	Chlorine = $M/83$;	Temp. = 32.6.
Time in mins. ...	0 57 152 252	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	23.45 22.5 21.3 19.8	
Unimol. const.00031 .00028 .00029	Mean .00029

The constant in light is thus 0.00023.

Table XVI gives the temp. coefficients at different wave-lengths.

TABLE XVI.

Wave-length ...	436 $\mu\mu$	404 $\mu\mu$	366.5 $\mu\mu$
Temp. coefficient ...	$\frac{.00047}{.00034} = 1.38$	$\frac{.00022}{.00017} = 1.29$	$\frac{.00023}{.00021} = 1.10$

The temperature coefficient thus increases with increase in wavelength. This is in accordance with the ideas of Tolman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 2285).

Influence of intensity on reaction rate.—The intensities of monochromatic radiation obtained by using filters being very small, influence of intensity could not be determined in monochromatic light as the reaction cell could not be pushed nearer. The influence of intensity was, therefore, determined by using white light. The reaction cell was placed at a distance of 17 cm. from the mercury lamp and a water filter of 4 cm. was employed as before. The incident intensity in this case was therefore half 144/289 the intensity in previous cases (Tables II-VII). Only two typical results are given below.

TABLE XVII.

Cinnamic acid = $M/30$;		Chlorine = $M/86$;		Temp. = 22.6° .	
Time in mins. ...	0	25	55	85	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	23.1	20.4	17.8	15.3	
Unimol. const.0022	.0021	.0021	Mean .0021

TABLE XVIII.

Cinnamic acid = $M/60$;		Chlorine = $M/143$;		Temp. = 22.6° .		
Time in mins. ...	0	15	40	70	125	
$N/500$ Thiosulphate in c.c.	14.1	13.25	13.0	10.8	8.9	
Unimol. const.0018	.0018	.0017	.0016	Mean .0017

Mean of the two series is 0.0019. The velocity constant with double this intensity (Tables II-VII) was 0.0039. The relative intensities in the two series of experiments were also measured by means of the Moll-thermopile using a 50 ohms resistance in series. With the mercury lamp at 12 cm., the deflection was 115 mm. and with the mercury lamp at 17 cm., the deflection was 64 divisions. The ratio of the intensities was thus 1.8. The ratio of the corresponding velocity constants is 2. The velocity constant is thus directly proportional to the intensity of light.

Theoretical.

The main features of the reaction are the following. The reaction is unimolecular with respect to chlorine and the velocity is unaffected by changes in the concentration of the acceptor so long as it does not fall too low. The quantum efficiency is greater than unity and gradually increases with increase in frequency. The problem now is to explain the observed facts.

The formation of excited chlorine molecules on absorption of light is not supported by experimental evidence. Bonhoeffer's experiment on the sensitisation of ozone decomposition by chlorine (*Z. Physik*, 1923, **13**, 94) and other experiments (*Physikal. Z.*, 1923, **24**, 504) indicate a long life of activated chlorine. One naturally expects fluorescence from excited molecules with a long life. Wood, and recently Kistiakowsky (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 2194) failed to observe fluorescence in gaseous chlorine. The present author also tried to detect fluorescence in carbon tetrachloride solutions of chlorine (*M/200*, *M/10*). Wood's method (*Phil. Mag.*, 1928, **6**, 729 for taking Raman spectra was employed. While the Raman lines due to carbon tetrachloride including the anti-Stokes lines appeared after half an hour's exposure, three hours' exposure failed to show any fluorescence band due to chlorine.

On the other hand Franck's hypothesis of dissociation of chlorine molecules by absorption of wave-length shorter than 4785\AA is well supported by experiments. (Dymond, *Z. Physik*, 1925, **34**, 553; Kuhn, *Z. Physik*, 1926, **39**, 77). In the present case since the quantum efficiency is greater than unity, a chain reaction is indicated. We shall assume that the primary action of light is to dissociate the chlorine molecule into an excited and normal atom.

Our experiments show that the rate of reaction is unaffected even when the cinnamic acid concentration falls low. This shows a long life of excited chlorine. It thus indicates that the reverse reaction $\text{Cl}^* + \text{Cl} = \text{Cl}_2$ is extremely slow in carbon tetrachloride. This is in accordance with the views of Kisiakowsky (*loc. cit.*) who explains the absence of Budde effect in dry chlorine by assuming that, in the absence of water vapour, the reaction $\text{Cl}^* + \text{Cl} \rightarrow \text{Cl}_2$,

which gives rise to the heating effect, does not take place. In our experiments the carbon tetrachloride and chlorine were fairly dry and we take it, therefore, that the reverse reaction $\text{Cl}^* + \text{Cl} \rightarrow \text{Cl}_2$ does not take place. The concentration of excited chlorine atom is thus directly proportional to the light absorbed, *i.e.*, the intensity of incident light. We are thus able to explain why the unimolecular constant should be directly proportional to the intensity of light.

The excited Cl^* atom then combines with a cinnamic acid molecule to form the monochloride which carries the energy of excitation. Indicating a cinnamic acid molecule by *A*, the following reactions take place.

It is thus clear that the quantum efficiency should be greater than unity. The normal chlorine atom produced in (1) probably also forms ACl (not activated) because of the unsaturated nature of cinnamic acid but the unexcited ACl formed cannot produce a chain similar to reaction (3) and does not, therefore, increase the quantum yield per quantum. Such unactivated ACl molecules will react in the following way.

Why the quantum efficiency should increase with increase in frequency has got to be explained. It is known that a quantum of light of $478.5\mu\mu$ is sufficient to dissociate the chlorine molecule. A quantum of higher frequency increases the kinetic energy of the excited chlorine atom and therefore, of the monochloride formed. If we assume that the length of the chain is proportional to the energy associated with the ACl^* formed, we can explain the increase in quantum efficiency with increase in frequency. The idea is similar to the concept of hot molecules of Christiansen and Kramers (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, **104**, 451).

Summary.

(1) The kinetics of the photochemical reaction between chlorine and cinnamic acid in carbon tetrachloride have been studied in white

light and also in monochromatic light. The reaction gives a uni-molecular constant with respect to chlorine which is unaffected by changes in concentration of cinnamic acid and chlorine.

(2) The temperature coefficient is 1.1 at $366.5\mu\mu$, 1.29 at $404\mu\mu$, 1.38 at $436\mu\mu$. The quantum efficiency is 2 at $436\mu\mu$, 4 at $404\mu\mu$ and 7 at $366.5\mu\mu$. The following mechanism explains observed facts

(3) An explanation is given for the increase in quantum efficiency with increase in frequency.

(4) A solution of chlorine in carbon tetrachloride exhibited no fluorescence.

My best thanks are due to Prof. J. C. Ghosh for his kind interest and many valuable suggestions.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY.

Received February 27, 1929.